

Datum 2022-10-25
Dnr RAÄ-2021-3125
Handläggare: Elyse Canosa

μ- XRF Instrument Report

Sample Identification Code

RAÄ Dnr RAÄ-2021-3125

Sample

Description of sample Three types of samples were investigated:

- 1) Canvas paintings created with modern paints made by the guest colleague (see Figure 2. Made of multiple paint layers (see Figure 1).
- 2) Paintings on Melinex made by the guest colleague, created with the same modern paints as the canvas paintings (see Figure 3). Made of multiple paint layers (Figure 1).
- 3) Paint squeezed directly out of the tubes used to create the canvas and Melinex paintings. Squeezed directly onto a Melinex sheet.

All analysis performed on the canvas and Melinex were performed on unaged samples (i.e. samples before they were placed in the climate chamber or samples that were never placed in the climate chamber)

Sample	Description
Lead white	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Umber tempera	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Ivory black	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Cobalt blue	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Alizarin crimson	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Chrome green	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Raw umber	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Zinc white	Paint squeezed directly from tube on to Melinex
Canvas 1CA	Paint layers on canvas (from canvas to surface): Lead white + zinc white (linseed oil), umber (water based tempera), alizarin crimson + zinc white (linseed oil), cobalt blue + zinc white (egg tempera), chrome green + zinc white (linseed oil). Cobalt blue layer is thick. Not aged. See Figure
Canvas 2CA	Paint layers on canvas (from canvas to surface): Lead white (linseed oil), umber (water based tempera), alizarin crimson (linseed oil), cobalt blue (egg tempera), chrome green (linseed oil). Cobalt blue layer is thick. Not aged. See Figure
Canvas 3CB	Paint layers on canvas (from canvas to surface): Lead white (linseed oil), umber (water based tempera), alizarin crimson

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	(linseed oil), chrome green (linseed oil). Not aged. See Figure
Canvas ground	Bare canvas with no paint layers. Not aged.
Melinex	Bare Melinex with no paint layers. Not aged.
Melinex 1MA	Paint layers on Melinex (from Melinex to surface): Lead white + zinc white (linseed oil), umber (water based tempera), alizarin crimson + zinc white (linseed oil), cobalt blue + zinc white (egg tempera), chrome green + zinc white (linseed oil). Cobalt blue layer is thick. Not aged. See Figure
Melinex 1MB	Paint layers on Melinex (from Melinex to surface): Lead white + zinc white (linseed oil), umber (water based tempera), alizarin crimson + zinc white (linseed oil), cobalt blue + zinc white (egg tempera), chrome green + zinc white (linseed oil). Cobalt blue layer is thin. Not aged. See Figure

Age Modern paints and canvas

Material Linseed oil paints and water based tempera paints on primed canvas or bare Melinex. Paints used include:

- Lead white (linseed oil)
- Umber (tempera)
- Ivory black (linseed oil)
- Cobalt blue (linseed oil)
- Alzarin cromson (linseed oil)
- Chrome green (linseed oil)
- Raw umber (linseed oil)
- Zinc white (linseed oil)

Figure 1: paint layers incorporated in the Melinex and canvas paintings made by the guest colleague

Figure 2: Canvas painting made by guest colleague and XRF sample locations

Figure 3: Melinex paintings made by guest colleague and XRF sample locations

Purpose

The paintings are intended to replicate a section of a Richard Bergh painting using similar paints. XRF is therefore used to determine if the paints used are in fact composed of the correct materials needed to replicate the Richard Bergh painting. Additionally, there is a strong interest in the effect of zinc white on the formation of cracks in the paintings. It may be possible that zinc white could inherently be contained in the paints purchased to create the replicas. XRF is used to observe if there are zinc traces in any of the individual paints.

Method

Sample preparation: The following samples were squeezed directly from paint tubes onto Melinex and analyzed without drying; single point analysis performed:

- Lead white (linseed oil)

- Umber (tempera)
- Ivory black (linseed oil)
- Cobalt blue (linseed oil)
- Alzarin crimson (linseed oil)
- Chrome green (linseed oil)
- Raw umber (linseed oil)
- Zinc white (linseed oil)

The following samples were analyzed directly on the object (canvas painting or Melinex painting); single point analysis performed:

- Canvas ground
- Melinex

The following samples were analyzed directly on the object (canvas painting or Melinex painting); z-axis line scans in a single location:

- Canvas 1CA
- Canvas 2CA
- Canvas 3CB
- Melinex 1MA
- Melinex 1MB

Note that z-axis scans were started at bottom layers (layer 1 in figure 1) and ended at the top layer (layer 6 in Figure 1).

Instrument Parameters

Parameters used for samples squeezed directly from paint tubes onto Melinex:

μ -XRF Artax 800, Mo X-ray tube with polycapillary lens, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

single point analysis (spot size <100 μ m)

line scan (lateral resolution <100 μ m)

elemental 2D mapping

quantification, MQuant Calib, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

quantification with standards

Voltage 50 KV

Current 600 μ A

Scan time per point 14 s

Number of measurement points 3

Spot distance

Scan area

Total scan time

Filter no filter Al 315 μm Mo 12.50 μm other _____

Lens 0.060

Atmosphere air He for light element detection

- **Parameters used for samples measured on the canvas or Melinex paintings
(points 1CA, 2CA, 3CB, 1MA, 1MB)**

μ -XRF Artax 800, Mo X-ray tube with polycapillary lens, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

single point analysis (spot size <100 μm)

line scan (lateral resolution <100 μm)

elemental 2D mapping

quantification, MQuant Calib, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

quantification with standards

Voltage 50 KV

Current 600 μA

Scan time per point 10 s

Number of measurement points 100

Spot distance 0.03 mm

Scan area

Total scan time 16 minutes

Filter no filter Al 315 μm Mo 12.50 μm other _____

Lens 0.060

Atmosphere air He for light element detection

Qualitative Results

Samples squeezed directly from paint tube onto Melinex, single point analysis:

Lead white

Umber

Ivory black

Cobalt blue

Alzarin crimson

Chrome green

Raw umber

Zinc white

Single point analysis of the canvas ground and Melinex:

Melinex:

Canvas ground:

Line scan Results

For all graphs, x-axis begins at layer 1 and ends at layer 6.

Canvas 1CA

Canvas 2CA

Canvas 3CB

Melinex 1MA

Melinex 1MB

